

Position Paper

Vision on Publication Culture

*Universities of
The Netherlands*

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Preface

This position paper Vision on Publication Culture brings together ongoing initiatives aimed at promoting a new culture of scholarly publishing. The paper emphasises the importance of establishing institution-wide principles and guidelines as a foundation for a new publication culture, while allowing flexibility to account for contextual and disciplinary differences.

By providing a common framework at the national level, the paper introduces a coordinated national approach to support universities, faculties and research institutes in making informed policy choices regarding scholarly publishing.

The ultimate goal of the envisioned publication culture is to strengthen research by promoting the production of research outputs that genuinely advance knowledge and benefit society. This goal can be achieved only if research is conducted with integrity. Reforming publication culture plays a key role in safeguarding and strengthening this integrity.

Existing ambitions and initiatives in the areas of open access, open science, and Recognition & Rewards are brought together in this position paper, fostering alignment and shared understanding. These ambitions and initiatives are explicitly connected with broader themes, including collective infrastructures, research integrity, artificial intelligence (AI), and knowledge security.

This position paper seeks to stimulate dialogue within institutions, while taking into account national and international developments in research assessment and scholarly publishing. Similar to the [Strategy Evaluation Protocol](#)¹, the paper provides a flexible framework that supports both institution-wide consistency and locally tailored strategic choices. Within the framework offered by the paper, universities, faculties, and research institutes can adapt their approach to specific contexts and disciplinary norms while remaining aligned with academic core values and the principles of open science and Recognition & Rewards.

In short, this position paper lays out a shared foundation for publication culture across institutions, creating space for context-specific implementation that balances common standards with the diversity of research practices.

¹ The Strategy Evaluation Protocol (SEP), developed by KNAW, NWO, and UNL, provides the core quality assurance framework for evaluating university research through periodic external assessments of research units and research groups.

1. *What do we want to achieve?*

The overarching aim of this position paper is to promote a publication culture that strengthens research integrity, so that research outputs are reliable and reproducible, and genuinely advance knowledge and benefit society.

Publication culture refers to the norms, values, practices, and expectations surrounding the publication of scholarly work. It concerns why, where, when, and how researchers publish their work, and the implications this has for their careers, the quality of research, and the accessibility of knowledge.

This position paper offers a guideline for future policy developments related to scholarly publishing. This includes the development of strategies and policies for open science, criteria for dissertations, policies related to Recognition & Rewards (e.g., appointment criteria and career paths), and agreements between university libraries and internal units within universities regarding collection development and publisher deals.

Rather than promoting specific publishing approaches, this position paper aims to support universities, faculties, and research institutes in making policy choices related to scholarly publishing in a well-informed coordinated way that aligns with academic core values and the principles of open science and Recognition & Rewards.

1.1 **Vision for a new publication culture**

By 2030, we envision a new publication culture that promotes the progress of science and advances knowledge for the benefit of society. In this culture, research outputs in all their forms² will be recognised as essential outcomes of scholarly work. They will be valued for their contribution to research quality and integrity and for their societal relevance and impact. Research outputs will be shared as openly and as early as possible, facilitating transparency and accountability and enabling maximal reuse. Research outputs will serve as crucial building blocks for trust between science and society.

In this new publication culture, the quality, integrity, openness, and scientific and societal relevance of research outputs will outweigh their quantity and the prestige of their publication venues. Evaluation and recognition will be driven by the substantive contribution of scholarly works to scientific progress and societal challenges. Publication practices will reflect the values of open science, research integrity, and Recognition & Rewards, and will incorporate a broad vision on impact³. These values will be firmly embedded in the everyday practices of researchers across all disciplines.

2 Including but not limited to narrative outputs (e.g., journal articles, preprints, conference papers, books and book chapters, dissertations, professional publications, etc), datasets, software, models, protocols (e.g., research protocols, instrumentation protocols, intervention protocols, data analysis protocols, test protocols, etc), lab journals, field notes, technical designs, valorisation products, results of public engagement activities, and teaching materials. In addition, validating and reproducing previous research and publishing null or negative results is included as well.

3 As agreed by the Dutch Universities in April 2025.

1.2 Consequences of a new publication culture

The new publication culture we envision will increase openness and transparency in scholarly publishing, promote research integrity, strengthen trust in science, enhance digital autonomy, and safeguard academic freedom. In this new culture, the Netherlands will have a sustainable open access policy that serves the missions of its researchers and research units, an incentive system that truly promotes quality over quantity, and an ecosystem of community-driven infrastructures that support this.

In practice, this entails:

- **Scientific progress with integrity:** Research outputs will be shared as openly and as early as possible, increasing the speed of scientific progress while ensuring transparency, reproducibility, and accountability.
- **Assessment based on quality rather than quantity:** Researchers will be assessed based on the substantive contributions of their work, not the quantity of outputs or the prestige of publication venues. Academic core values such as rigour, integrity, openness, and scientific and societal impact will be leading.

- **Digital autonomy and open infrastructures:** Researchers will be supported by an ecosystem of open community-driven publication infrastructures. This will reduce the dependence on commercial or revenue-driven publishers and ensure the long-term accessibility of research outputs. It will also strengthen academic control over the organisation and the cost of publication processes, safeguarding the interests of researchers and society.
- **Recognition of diverse outputs:** A broad spectrum of research outputs will be recognised as integral contributions to science. This includes research articles, datasets, software, preregistrations, policy reports, etc. Peer review will increasingly be performed after publication rather than before, and openness will increasingly be the norm in peer review. Peer review activities will be explicitly recognised.

In summary, the Netherlands will move towards a publication culture in which scientific progress is accelerated through openness, societal trust is strengthened through transparency and accountability, and costs are contained through collective investment in public infrastructures. The culture of publishing and the broader culture of science will be fully aligned, and research will be conducted, shared, and assessed in ways that foster both scientific excellence and societal value.

2. Why is a new publication culture *needed*?

An open and responsible publication culture is fundamental to scientific progress. It is a key condition for safeguarding and strengthening research integrity at a time when it is under increasing pressure from metric-driven “publish or perish” incentives, predatory journals, paper mills, AI-generated or fabricated content, and other questionable research practices.

Publication culture does not only shape why, where, when, and how research is disseminated. Incentive structures embedded in publication culture also affect the attitudes and behaviours of researchers and the everyday research practices resulting from this.

Research is conducted to advance knowledge and benefit society. However, research can achieve this goal only if it is produced, communicated, and evaluated with integrity. Reforming our publication culture is central to safeguarding research integrity and strengthening trust in the scientific record.

The current publication culture suffers from several structural problems, as discussed below.

2.1 Reproducibility and research integrity

In the current publication culture, several mutually reinforcing mechanisms undermine reproducibility and create opportunities and incentives for questionable research practices. The pressure to publish, combined with a strong focus on the prestige of publication venues, discourages replication studies and the publication of negative or null results. As a result, published work often lacks reproducibility.

The same mechanisms increase the risk of scientific misconduct. Concerns about research integrity have intensified worldwide, as a result of the rapid growth of so-called paper mills and the emergence of AI-generated or fabricated research. At the same time, the rise of journals that charge publication fees without conducting rigorous peer review, often referred to as predatory journals, further erodes research integrity. By exploiting the pressure to publish, these journals facilitate the dissemination of low-quality or fraudulent research, weakening trust in the scientific record.

2.2 Unsustainable pressure to publish

Career advancement in academia often hinges on the number of publications (“publish or perish”) and the prestige or impact factor of the journals in which researchers publish. This creates strong incentives, particularly for early-career researchers, to prioritise quantity over quality.

The pressure to publish leads to undesirable practices such as avoiding high-risk or long-term projects, hesitating to engage in interdisciplinary work, “salami-slicing” research to boost publication counts, and neglecting negative results or replication studies. This dynamic fuels a continuous increase in scholarly output, which in turn undermines the financial sustainability of scholarly publishing, as costs continue to rise while budgets remain under pressure.

2.3 Lack of appreciation for diverse outputs

Traditional recognition and reward systems undervalue a broad range of scholarly contributions, including but not limited to datasets, software, preregistrations, peer review activities, and policy reports. These outputs are rarely credited in hiring, tenure, and promotion processes.

Metric-driven evaluation practices further reinforce a narrow focus on journal articles, rendering other important formats, such as books and book chapters, comparatively invisible. Moreover, efforts by researchers to adopt more open and sustainable publishing practices are often insufficiently recognised, limiting incentives for systemic change.

2.4 Inequities in access to journals and other publication venues

While open access aims to democratise knowledge, many prevailing models rely on article processing charges and book processing charges, putting financial burdens onto authors. Researchers affiliated with institutions that have limited resources, as well as those in low- and middle-income countries, often struggle to afford these fees, resulting in inequitable publishing opportunities. Even within relatively well-funded research systems such as in the Netherlands, disparities in funding options exist across disciplines and organisational units. Consequently, researchers with fewer resources remain underrepresented in high-prestige publication venues, perpetuating cycles of limited visibility and constrained access to funding.

2.5 Peer review crisis

Scholarly publishing remains a slow process in which research findings are typically shared only at the end of a project and only after a lengthy non-transparent peer review process. The growing volume of research outputs has outpaced the availability of qualified reviewers, leading to further delays and threatening the quality and rigour of peer review.

Peer review processes also exhibit regional and institutional biases. Articles rejected by one journal are frequently resubmitted elsewhere with minimal revision, yet reviews are rarely shared across journals. This results in repeated rounds of peer review for the same work, further burdening an already overstretched system. Given the scarcity of knowledgeable reviewers, the expectation that all articles can undergo rigorous, in-depth peer review is increasingly unrealistic.

3. Guiding principles for a new publication culture

Academic core values form the foundation for scholarly work. Principles such as academic freedom, research integrity, and openness define the standards by which scholarly work is conducted and shared.

As we move towards a more open and responsible research system, these values must be reflected in the way we publish and disseminate the knowledge we produce. Building on ongoing efforts around open science and initiatives such as the Recognition & Rewards programme, [CoARA](#)⁴, and [DORA](#)⁵, we seek to establish a publication culture that strengthens both scientific quality and societal relevance.

This new publication culture is guided by three key principles: Fit-for-Purpose, Open, and Sustainable. Below is an explanation of what each guiding principle entails.

3.1 Fit-for-Purpose

- Publishing research is an essential step for us to share our work, receive feedback, create impact, and advance knowledge. We publish our research in ways that are fit-for-purpose and that enable us to engage with the most relevant audiences.
- Depending on the nature of our research and the audiences that we aim to engage with, we may publish our research in a variety of different ways, for instance as an article in a peer-reviewed journal, on a preprint server, or in an institutional repository, as a book, as a policy report, as a blog post, within a data repository, etc.
- We may publish our research in Dutch, in English, or in other relevant languages.

⁴ The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) is a collective of organisations committed to reforming the methods and processes by which research, researchers, and research organisations are evaluated.

⁵ The San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA) is adopted by KNAW, UNL and NWO.

3.2 Open

- We publish our research and the underlying materials (e.g., datasets and software) as openly as possible, ensuring equal access to scientific knowledge worldwide.
- We share research materials as early as possible to ensure verifiability and integrity, complying with the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.
- We foster open dialogue with science and society by sharing preliminary results, welcoming feedback and facilitating open peer review. We strive to continuously improve our research based on the input we receive.
- We seek to strengthen digital autonomy in our publishing practices by retaining ownership and copyright of our research outputs and by using public infrastructures.

3.3 Sustainable

- We support sustainable career trajectories for researchers by recognising and rewarding all research outputs that contribute to the strategic goals of a research team or research unit. We value diversity in publishing practices.
- We acknowledge that research is a team effort and ensure that all contributors to a research output, with their different roles, skills and expertise, are appropriately recognised.
- We recognise the cost of publishing and actively support publishing models that are financially sustainable for all stakeholders involved.

4. Reference *framework* for a new publication culture

The guiding principles discussed above define the values and direction of a new publication culture. We now turn to the practical implementation.

This section provides a reference framework for research units, researchers, and support professionals to translate the guiding principles into context-specific publication practices and strategies. The framework prioritises quality over quantity and recognises the diversity of academic disciplines, missions, and publication formats.

Differentiation – across research, education, and societal engagement – enables a richer and more inclusive understanding of academic knowledge production. By embracing this diversity, institutions and researchers can shape publication practices and strategies that are both meaningful within their own contexts and aligned with the broader vision for a Fit-for-Purpose, Open, and Sustainable publication culture.

4.1 Audience & Quality

Research is published in a way that enables reaching the relevant audiences, in line with the quality standards expected by these audiences.

- Consider the target audience for each research output and choose a journal, platform, or repository that enables reaching this audience.
- Take into account the quality standards of different journals, platforms, and repositories, and consider what types of quality control (e.g., closed peer

review, open peer review, or other evaluation processes) are required or desirable for each research output.

- Contribute to the development of domain/discipline-specific quality standards for different types of research outputs (e.g., data and models). Make sure these quality standards address the use of AI in scholarly publishing.
- Encourage researchers to take an active role in quality control processes in scholarly publishing, both peer review processes and other evaluation processes. Recognise researchers for their contributions to these processes.
- Consider the relevant quality standards in a domain when developing domain/institute-specific publication strategies.

4.2 Openness & Timeliness

Research is published in an open and timely way.

- Make openness the norm for sharing all research outputs (“as open as possible, as closed as necessary”), including the use of open licences. Ensure that openness is practised responsibly, with appropriate quality checks, accurate open metadata, and secure handling of sensitive information.

- Make an informed decision about the phase in the research process in which outputs are shared: from the start of the research process (e.g., open drafting), as early as possible in the research process (e.g., pre-registration and modular publishing), before peer review (e.g., preprinting), or after peer review. Encourage early sharing to maximise the impact of research and to make the research process more transparent, thus strengthening research integrity by enabling scrutiny, verification, and reuse throughout the research process.
- Encourage ownership/copyright retention, for instance by implementing an institutional rights retention policy and/or a workflow that safeguards ownership/copyright retention for early-phase outputs (e.g., submitted manuscripts and author accepted manuscripts).
- Encourage uploading of research outputs and the associated materials to the university research information system and/or repository, safeguarding the openness and long-term preservation of outputs. Encourage uploading of the metadata of an output if the output itself cannot be uploaded.
- Share research outputs in a findable, accessible, and machine-readable way (e.g., FAIR principles), and make sure outputs are indexed in ways that allow them to be recognised and rewarded.
- Promote open forms of evaluation of research outputs, such as open peer review and publish-review-curate.

4.3 Cost effectiveness

Research is published in a way that safeguards financial sustainability and cost control of publication infrastructures.

- Make informed decisions about where, when, and how to publish research outputs. Promote quality over quantity. Avoid excessive publishing.
- Make sure the costs of a publication channel are proportionate to the value of the services offered by the publication channel.
- Consider cost implications when developing domain/institute-specific publication strategies (e.g., allowing payments of article processing charges only for high-quality publication channels, and/or encouraging diamond open access if suitable diamond publication channels are available).

5. What is needed to *change* our publication culture?

Realising a sustainable, open, and quality-driven publication culture requires structural change in how we organise, conduct, support, and reward scholarly publishing, from the infrastructures we use to the incentives we create and the governance systems we design.

The following five conditions, aligned with the [UNL Open Science Agenda](#), outline the key requirements for achieving a change in publication culture.

5.1 Open and sovereign infrastructures

An open and responsible publication culture can be realised only if it is enabled by robust, open, and community-driven infrastructures.

This means:

- Investing in federated repositories, metadata services, and national platforms that ensure discoverability, interoperability, and long-term accessibility of all types of research outputs (with optional post-publication review and appropriate metrics for recognition), in alignment with ideas for [integrated infrastructures](#) and the [Strategic Plan Integral Infrastructure for Open Science \(SPII\)](#).
- Investing in innovative new infrastructure initiatives, such as initiatives for open peer review and the publish-review-curate model as well as the [Netherlands University Presses network](#), which develops shared editorial, dissemination, and quality assurance services for diamond open access.
- Strengthening digital autonomy by reducing dependence on commercial or revenue-driven publishers and embedding scholarly publishing within public non-profit infrastructures, including collaborative infrastructures at the European level, such as [Open Research Europe](#). Prioritising digital autonomy is critical in light of geopolitical developments, concerns around state influence on digital infrastructures, and the dominant role of big-tech companies in the rapidly evolving AI landscape.

- Guaranteeing cost management by building on existing infrastructures, such as institutional repositories, and connecting them through central indexing and dissemination services with transparent quality control mechanisms.

5.2 Support, skills, and competencies

A new publication culture requires both researchers and professional staff to be equipped with the right knowledge and skills.

This involves:

- Training and educating researchers and professional staff in responsible publishing practices, the FAIR principles, (open) peer review, and the use of open infrastructures. Different disciplines and research units may require different approaches to training and education.
- Expanding the role of digital competence centres, libraries, and research support offices to provide hands-on guidance.
- Establishing institutional quality assurance processes to verify the accuracy and completeness of the metadata of research outputs, to strengthen adherence to the FAIR principles, to ensure responsible use of AI tools, to comply with purpose limitations, and to prevent the publication of sensitive information.
- Developing institutional publication frameworks, such as those already underway at several universities (e.g., Groningen, Leiden, and Wageningen), to help researchers and research units make informed publication choices while respecting disciplinary diversity.

5.3 Norm-setting with the academic community

Lasting change requires the development of new norms owned by the academic community itself. These norms should reflect an awareness that publication practices serve the integrity and trustworthiness of research, so that research outputs genuinely advance knowledge and benefit society.

This means:

- Encouraging researchers to make their scholarly works openly available as early as possible, and stimulating them to openly share different types of research outputs (e.g., datasets, software, and preregistrations) as an integral part of the research process.
- Raising awareness of the costs and the problems of the current publication culture, and ensuring both individual and collective publication decisions are informed by this awareness.
- Broadening the scope of peer review, focusing on learning and improvement. Transparency, openness, and diversity of perspectives need to become the norm in peer review. It needs to be recognised that peer review is more important for some research outputs than for others. In line with the ambition to share research outputs as early as possible, a transition from pre-publication peer review to post-publication peer review is needed.
- Engaging researchers, professional staff, and research managers across disciplines to co-create shared values for scholarly publishing, and exploring the actions researchers can take in their different roles – as authors, reviewers, editors, and readers – to put these values into practice.

5.4 Recognition for new practices

Researchers can be expected to embrace new publication practices only if they are recognised and rewarded for doing so.

This requires:

- Piloting and implementing criteria that incentivise new publication practices, also in line with the Recognition & Rewards programme and CoARA, as already underway at several Dutch universities.
- Replacing quantity-driven metrics with quality-focused indicators aligned with the mission of a research unit. These indicators need to be based on openly available data, in line with the [Barcelona Declaration](#) on Open Research Information.
- Introducing “next-generation” indicators for non-traditional types of scholarly works and using these indicators to recognise the value of a wider range of research outputs.
- Providing recognition for researchers and research teams that pioneer innovative publishing models (e.g., diamond open access, open peer review, and publish-review-curate).

5.5 Anchoring in policy

A new publication culture needs to be embedded in institutional and national policy frameworks. Policies should reflect that the primary aim of a new publication culture is to improve the quality, integrity, and societal relevance of research, with open access, open science, and Recognition & Rewards serving as instruments to achieve this aim.

This entails:

- Making sure institutional and national policies, such as policies of NWO and ZonMw, the Strategy Evaluation Protocol, and the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, explicitly address publication culture as part of a broader perspective on open science.
- Aligning career policies with a new publication culture, especially for early-career researchers.
- Creating policies that safeguard research integrity, cost transparency, and responsible use of resources.
- Promoting financially sustainable publication practices in open access and open science policies, for instance by discouraging hybrid and gold open access models while promoting preprinting, post-publication peer review, diamond open access, subscribe-to-open, etc.
- Developing policies for funding community-driven publication infrastructures, including the reallocation of financial resources in line with the choices research units make in a new publication culture.

Colophon

This position paper was developed at the initiative of the Chiefs Open Science of Dutch universities and prepared by a representative working group of experts.

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